

Linear correlations of false smut (*Ustilagoidea virens*) disease incidence (percent panicles with false smut) on 32 rice cultivars and plant and environmental factors.

	Correlation coefficient (<i>r</i>) ^a
Plant	
Plant height (cm)	-0.54*
Days to 50% flowering	0.095**
Environment ^a	
Maximum temp ^d (28.1°C)	-0.048
Minimum temp (20.1°C)	-0.040
Relative humidity (87.8%)	-0.321
Rainfall (1.4 mm)	-0.120
Cloudiness (1.74 h)	-0.176
Disease severity	
Number of false-smutted florets on the panicle with maximum infection	0.81*

^a P(0.05) = 0.349*. ^b Av of 32 d during flowering.

cant. Correlations with environmental factors during flowering (22 Aug-29 Sep) were negative and nonsignificant (see table).

Among cultivars, the positive correlation ($r = 0.81$) of number of smutted florets on the panicle with the most infected florets and percent false smutted panicles was significant. The relationship between number of smutted florets on the panicle with the most infected florets and percent panicles with false smut (regression coefficient $y = 1.26 + 0.763 x$) shows that, in assessing disease severity, one disease severity factor can be used to estimate another factor. ■

Bakanae and foot rot of rice in Punjab, Pakistan

L. K. Khokhar, National Agricultural Research Centre, Crop Diseases Research Institute, Islamabad, Pakistan

During a 1989 survey of rice crop diseases in Sialkot, Gujranwala, and Sheikhpura of Punjab Province, Basmati 385 growing in isolated farmers' fields showed symptoms similar to those of bakanae disease. Some of the plants had yellowish green, thin leaves and exhibited abnormal stem elongation, lower tillering, and rotting at the root-stem joint as well as at the first node.

Laboratory examination revealed the presence of *Fusarium moniliforme* Sheld., the imperfect stage of *Gibberella fijiikuroi* (identified on the basis of micro and macro conidia, micro conidiophores, and micro conidial chains). A pathogen-

icity test to fulfill the requirements of Koch's postulates confirmed *F. moniliforme* to be the causal organism.

This is the first report of this disease in Pakistan. ■

Efficacy of ethofenprox in preventing rice tungro (RTV) infection

N. V. Krishnaiah and A. Ghosh, Directorate of Rice Research, Rajendranagar, Hyderabad 500030, India

RTV transmitted by green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens* is one of the important diseases of rice in many parts of India. We studied the efficacy of ethofenprox (a new ether-derived insecti-

cide similar to synthetic pyrethroids) against GLH and RTV transmission.

Potted TN1 plants in controlled greenhouse conditions were sprayed with ethofenprox. At 0.01%, ethofenprox killed 78% of confined viruliferous adults within 30 min; plants sprayed with 0.01% recorded significantly lower RTV infection than plants sprayed with 0.05% monocrotophos (see table). GLH mortality within 30 min and RTV transmission were related; GLH mortality after 30 min was not related to RTV transmission. ■

Effect of ethofenprox and monocrotophos on green leafhoppers and RTV transmission.^a

Insecticide	GLH mortality (%)				RTV infection (%)
	0.5 h	1.0 h	4.0 h	24 h	
Ethofenprox 0.01%	78 a	87 a	95 a	100 a	53 a
Monocrotophos 0.05%	22 b	58 a	93 a	100 a	80 b
Untreated control	0 c	0 b	0 b	2 b	100 c

^a In a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

Integrated pest management—insects

Mutual interference among wolf spider adult females

K. L. Heong and E. G. Rubia, Entomology Department, IIRI

In ricefields, wolf spiders *Lycosa pseudoannulata* respond to high densities of prey, particularly brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål). This increases the chances that spiders will encounter each other while hunting for prey. That may decrease searching efficiency per predator and increase a tendency toward aggression, cannibalism, and outward dispersal. Such encounters between searching predators are often called "mutual interference."

We conducted laboratory experiments to measure mutual interference among wolf spiders and to determine the effect of hopper density on encounters between

spiders. Freshly emerged BPH adult females were placed inside mylar cages (19-cm diam, 55-cm ht) with 5 tillers of TN1 potted rice plants at densities of 5, 10, 20, 30, and 60 BPH/cage. They were exposed to 1, 2, or 3 freshly emerged adult female wolf spiders for 24 h. There were 5 replications.

Searching efficiency per spider, a , over the experimental period was computed as

$$a = 1/P \ln [N/(N-N_a)]$$

where a is searching efficiency, P is predator number, N is initial number of BPH, and N_a is number of BPH attacked. Log of a was plotted against log of P to obtain a linear regression. The resulting relationship of this linear model is

$$\log a = \log Q - m \log P$$

where Q and m are constants, characteristic of the predator.